

Thermo-mechanical response and form-stability of a fully metallic composite phase change material: Dilatometric tests and finite element analysis

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ABSTRACT

Composite Phase Change Materials (C-PCMs), such as immiscible Al-Sn alloys are designed to store and release heat as a result of the phase transformation of one of the phases, i.e., Sn in this case. The volume changes induced by melting and solidification of the low-melting Sn phase as well as the different thermal expansion of solid Al and Sn phases induces stress fields during thermal cycles. Repeated experimental dilatometric tests were performed on the above C-PCM to check their microstructural stability as well as its effect on their form-stability, i. e., capability to recover the initial shape under various potential cyclic service conditions.

Analysis of the thermo-mechanical behaviour of the two phases, as well as the overall one, have been investigated under the simple thermal profiles reproducing dilatometric tests. A finite element model of fully dense Al-Sn C-PCM, where a single spherical inclusion of Sn is surrounded by Al matrix, is generated and numerical thermo-mechanical analysis is performed. The thermal-dependence of elastoplastic-behaviour, thermal expansivity and other thermophysical properties of the 2 solid phases has been modelled, together with compressibility of liquid Sn. The simulations illustrate the overall material behaviour as well as the local thermomechanical response. The results for the slopes of elongation vs temperature curves agree well with experimental data from dilatometric tests, for which form-stability is observed from the third cycle. The results also suggested that the plastic deformation of the only regions of Al phase surrounding the Sn inclusion accommodates its expansion during heating and melting. In these latter regions, at the end of a dilatometric cycle, compressive strain in radial direction reaches a maximum value of 0.1 %, higher than overall strains.

1. Introduction

Phase Change Materials (PCMs) have the capability of storing/releasing thermal energy as latent heat during the occurrence of a phase transformation [1]. This makes them appealing materials for Thermal Energy Storage (TES), finding applications in the field of renewable power sources, where intermittently available sources concurrently push the research toward reliable energy storage systems [2]. The possibility to choose PCMs of various type (salts, organic, metallics) which allow the selection of the transformation temperature within a wide range of available ones, has extended the range of application of TES devices, to electronics, buildings, medical and other applications [3,4] A contribution to widen the application range of PCMs is given by the fact

that they can be used also as heat sink, and, more in general, in devices with Thermal Energy Management (TEM) purposes [5,6].

Among the phase transformation characterizing PCMs, solid-liquid is the most exploited one, since it allows the best compromise between high energy storability and low volume expansion. This means that in order to fully exploit its heat storage function, the PCM has to be in the molten state, in the high-temperature part of its concurrent heat storage and thermal cycle. Strategies have to be considered to tackle the issue of confinement of molten PCM and its related leakage, being them containers not interacting with molten PCM [7,8] or capsules from nano-to millimetric sizes [9–11]. More recently, the concept of avoiding leakage of molten PCM has been combined to that of form stability. This latter refers to the fact that the PCMs experience minimal volume changes

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induced by phase transition and original form recovery after a charge/discharge cycle [12–15]. Form-stable PCMs can be obtained by exploiting chemical- and/or physical-based approaches. For example, the formation of covalent [16], hydrogen [17] or van der Waals bonds [18] belongs to the first approach, whereas the exploitation of capillarity forces [17,19] to the second. More recent works on organic-based PCM have also added other geometry-related functionalities [20,21].

In the case of metallic PCMs, the target of confinement and form stability includes a further critical point, which is the tendency of liquid melt to interact with environment and confinement materials [13]. In this sense, the use of immiscible alloys, whose elements do not interact among themselves, can overcome the aforementioned issue. If properly manufactured, dispersing a low-melting phase in a high-melting matrix, immiscible alloys are suitable for both anti-leakage and form-stable purposes. A relevant example of these alloys derives from Al-Sn, for which various processing methods (ranging from powder metallurgy routes [22,23] or casting followed by medium-high cooling rates [24, 25]) were demonstrated to lead to suitable microstructures.

The 'way of working' of these phase change materials is characterized by the fact that, due to the immiscibility of the two elements of the binary system leads to the presence of phases whose composition roughly corresponds to the starting pure elements [22,24,26]. In the case of Al-Sn, this happens both in the temperature range in which the low-melting phase is solid, and above its melting temperature, as the phase which behaves as PCM is in the molten state. The liquid phase remains extremely rich of Sn up to about 30 °C above the onset of melting.

Indeed, the microstructure of Al-Sn alloy resembles the one of composite materials, where Al serves as matrix and the low-melting Sn as inclusion, properly dispersed in the former if produced with the suitable aforementioned processes. Indeed, Sn covers the role of the active PCM in the composite, whereas Al grants efficient heat transfer to the second phases, as well as load-bearing performances. The possibility to modify the Sn content in a relatively wide range of Al-Sn alloy keeping the abovementioned matrix/inclusion scheme, allows to tailor the thermal storage potential during thermal cycles. These materials can thus be considered as Composite Phase Change Materials (C-PCMs) in which the solid/liquid transformation only relates to the low-melting inclusions of Sn phase [23].

As for other composite materials, during this phase transformation as well as during other parts of the heating and cooling cycles which characterize the service conditions of C-PCMs, strains and thus stresses of thermal origin can arise among the different phases. In a previous work by the authors [27], numerical simulations on a physically representative material model are performed to understand thermal and mechanical behaviour of the single phases, as well as that of the material as a whole. They demonstrated that, elastoplastic strains of thermal origin arise in the composite due not only to the volume change associated to the Sn phase transition, but also to different coefficient of thermal expansions of the two phases [28,29]. They also demonstrated that plastic deformations can be triggered in both phases (but cancelled in Sn by its melting) in various part of the cycle. In the present paper, the analyses are widened to include two different holding temperatures and microstructural analyses in view of the evaluation of the form-stability of the alloy. Different thermal cycles, with various maximum target temperatures were thus considered to examine material behaviour.

2. Experimental analysis

2.1. Materials and material condition

The materials of Al –40 % mass Sn (a roughly corresponding to 80:20 volumetric ratio of the two phases at room temperature). The production process includes a preliminary induction melting in a graphite crucible under argon flux, to avoid oxidation. Once the alloy got completely molten, it was poured in a graining unit, which produced

small portions of solidified material of roughly ellipsoidal shape and some millimetres in size. Details on the processing, material shape and estimation of cooling rates are provided elsewhere [25]. Table 1 provides chemical composition of the granules used.

The material performance as PCM, including the experimental identification of the phase transition ranges during heating and cooling and corresponding latent heat values has been investigated during the first 10 cycles in a previous work by Bassani et al. [25]. The experimental temperature ranges and the latent heat values, obtained by DSC at 10°C/min, were close to those suggested by binary phase diagrams and ThermoCalc software calculations [25]. Specifically, the melting range was 228–235 °C melting enthalpy 31.8J/g. The material has been experimentally investigated in two different conditions: in the as-produced condition and after a heat treatment at 250 °C for 3 h in a protective Ar atmosphere. This latter was aimed at stabilizing the microstructure of the Al-Sn alloy and was selected following a previous work on molten Sn mobility in Al-Sn alloys [30]. By performing these treatments, the influence of out-of-equilibrium cooling present in the casting process was eliminated.

2.2. Dilatometric tests

For each material condition, specimens for dilatometric tests were produced by cutting by microtome the ends of the granules at their smaller cross-section in order to obtain the two flat and parallel surfaces needed for dilatometric tests (size of approximately 10 mm) and irregular cross-sections with average area roughly corresponding to a 5 mm edge. The actual length and density of the sample was measured by a calliper at the beginning of the test with a calliper and an Archimedes' balance, respectively.

Dilatometric tests were performed to assess the expansion/contraction of the material during a simulated working cycle, which includes phase transitions that could induce internal stresses.

Tests were run on a LINSEIS 75-V vertical dilatometer. All thermal cycles were characterized by heating cooling rates of 0.033 K/s (corresponding to 2 K/min) up to 270 °C or 250 °C, with a holding time of 5 min. The contact between the sample and the bar and rod system was assured by setting a controlled load of 200 mN, (leading roughly to pressure of 0.02 MPa pressure assuming a cross section of 5 mm edge through the sample).

During the test, the change of length ΔL was measured by the LVDT sensor of the machine, from which the thermal strain $\epsilon_{th} = \Delta L/L_0$ and its derivative with respect to the temperature $d(\Delta L/L_0)/dT$ were collected and analysed. Two sets of samples have been tested. A first set of samples, obtained from granules in the as-cast condition, was performed running cycles with holding temperature of 270 °C, repeating the heating/cooling for a different number of cycles for each sample (1, 2, 3, 6 and 10 cycles). These tests were aimed to investigate the form-stability of the material and its microstructural changes in the as-produced condition. The second set of dilatometric tests was carried out on samples obtained from granules heat treated at 250° for 3 h in order to stabilize the microstructure before dilatometric tests. Three cycles were run for each sample, reaching holding temperature of 250 or 270 °C. The highest holding temperature has been selected to better highlight possible differences in the relative change of length induced by the two selected thermal inputs.

2.3. Microstructural analyses

The as granules and tested dilatometric specimen were cut (these

Table 1
Chemical composition (mass%) of the Al-Sn alloy.

Al	Sn	Si	Fe	Mn	Mg	Zn	Ti
60.06	39.84	0.018	0.057	0.001	0.002	0.02	0.006

latter both longitudinally and transversally), cold-mounted and metallographically polished for microstructural analyses, performed at scanning electron microscope (SEM): The use of backscattered probe clearly revealed the white Sn-rich phase and the dark grey Al-rich phase, while discontinuities were in black colour. Quantitative analyses on the Sn phase morphology were performed by ImageJ [31] in view of identifying the average equivalent diameter globules, i.e., diameter of circles of equivalent area of Sn globules.

3. Modelling composite phase change material

In what follows the Al-20 vol%Sn C-PCM has been considered as a lattice material, where Al and Sn phases are arranged. The identification of the temperature-dependence of the thermal and mechanical properties of these two phases represents a crucial step for understanding the thermomechanical behaviour of the material. They will be thus presented as the first step for the development of the model. The identification of a representative volume of the composite material, and the set-up of the FEA of this material will be presented later, together with the boundary conditions adopted to reproduce various dilatometric tests in view of analysing the development stress and strain states in the two constituents of PCM.

3.1. Thermal properties of the phases

In the examined temperature range, the phases of the C-PCM can be approximated as pure Al and Sn. Indeed, the solubility of the two elements in each other is very low in the solid state. The same compositional stability is maintained also within some tenths of degree Cs above Sn melting temperature. The temperature-dependence of properties will be described separately for Al and Sn.

Aluminum does not undergo phase change in the temperature range considered. Temperature-dependent density, thermal conductivity and heat capacity can be indeed described well by linear or polynomial functions interpolating literature data. The temperature-dependence of the above properties are illustrated in Fig. 1 (density [32–34]), Fig. 2 (thermal expansion [29,34,35]), Fig. 3 (thermal conductivity [34,36]) and Fig. 4 (specific heat capacity [37,38]), where also Sn-data are presented for comparison purposes, and the literature sources are given.

Due to the need to model the behaviour of Sn, i.e., the active PCM of the composite, above and during the phase transition of the low-melting phase, the literature survey for the density, thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity was carried both in the liquid and in the solid range.

The Sn was assumed to melt in the temperature range from 228 to 232 °C, the latter (T_{liq} in Table 2) being the melting temperature of pure Sn and the former (T_{sol} in Table 2) that of the eutectic, whose composition is close to pure tin. Both thermal and mechanical properties of each phase vary as functions of temperature. The thermo-mechanical

analysis will be performed over a wide temperature range, i.e., from room temperature above Sn melting temperature. The temperature-dependence of density, thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity data collected from the literature are presented in Figs. 2–4, where the difference existing from solid to liquid Sn properties appears.

In the selected transition temperature range, the solidification of the Sn phase is considered within about 4 °C [39] and the related latent heat associated to of Sn solid/liquid phase transformation (Table 2), of 60 kJ/kg [40], is then assumed to be released during this temperature range.

3.2. Modelling of heat transfer and of Sn properties in the temperature range of solid/liquid Sn phase transformation

During the solid/liquid transformation of Sn the apparent heat capacity formulation as utilized in COMSOL is applied in this study. With this approach, the single heat transfer equation is solved for both phases with effective material properties. The latent heat of phase change for Sn is taken from Ref. [41] and directly modelled in the “Phase Change Material” interface of the software. The governing energy balance equation is formulated as follows:

$$\rho C_p (\partial T / \partial t) = \nabla \cdot (\kappa \nabla T) \quad (1)$$

where T is the absolute temperature [K], t is the time [s], c_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure [J/(kgK)], k is the thermal conductivity [W/(mK)], ρ is the density [kg/m³] and ∇ is the Hamiltonian (nabla) operator. Instead of adding a latent heat L in the energy balance equation exactly when the material reaches its phase change temperature T_{pc} , it is assumed that the transformation occurs in a temperature interval between $(T_{pc} - \Delta T/2)$ and $(T_{pc} + \Delta T/2)$.

In this interval, the material phase is modelled by a smooth function θ , representing the fraction of phase during transition. Considering a material that passes from solid to liquid state, $\theta_s = \theta$ represents the solid fraction that varies from 1 for temperature values below $(T_{pc} - \Delta T/2)$ to zero above $(T_{pc} + \Delta T/2)$. For the liquid phase it follows that $\theta_l = 1 - \theta$. The density, ρ , the specific enthalpy H , and the thermal conductivity k of the phase mixture are expressed as follows:

$$\rho = \theta_s \rho_s + \theta_l \rho_l \quad (2)$$

$$H = (\theta_s \rho_s H_s + \theta_l \rho_l H_l) / \rho \quad (3)$$

$$k = \theta_s k_s + \theta_l k_l \quad (4)$$

The apparent heat capacity is defined as follows:

$$c_p = \partial H / \partial T \quad (5)$$

With equations (2)–(5) the apparent heat capacity can be presented as a sum of equivalent c_{eq} and the latent c_L contributions as follows:

$$c_{eq} = (\theta_s \rho_s c_{ps} + \theta_l \rho_l c_{pl}) / \rho \quad (7)$$

Fig. 1. Density vs temperature for a) Al after [32,33] and b) Sn after [33,34].

Fig. 2. Linear thermal expansion coefficient vs temperature for a) Al after [29] and b) Sn after [34,35].

Fig. 3. Thermal conductivity vs. temperature for a) Al after [36] and b) Sn after [34,36].

Fig. 4. Heat capacity vs. temperature for a) Al after [37] and b) Sn after [38].

Table 2
Solid-liquid transformation data adopted for Sn phase, Sn, after [39,40].

Parameter	Value
$T_{solidus}$	228°C
T_m	230°C
$T_{liquidus}$	232°C
L	60 kJ/kg

$$c_L = (H_l - H_s)(d\alpha_m/dT) \tag{8}$$

$$\alpha_m = (\theta_l \rho_l - \theta_s \rho_s) / (2\rho) \tag{9}$$

In the case of sharp phase boundary, $(1 - \theta)$ becomes the Heavyside step function equal to 0 for $T < T_{pc}$ and 1 otherwise. In this case c_L is the enthalpy jump, L at temperature T_{pc} and

$$c_L = L (d\alpha_m/dT) \tag{10}$$

where the subscriptions s and l stand for solid and liquid. For the same phase (sn) The apparent heat capacity is defined as follows:

3.3. Mechanical properties of Al and Sn phases

The mechanical properties of the material here considered are those

that allow an easy description of the elastoplastic behaviour of the material at various temperatures. In particular, the temperature dependence of the elastic modulus, of the stress-strain curve descriptors for the 2 phases are presented.

To characterize the elastic regime sets of two properties must be defined. Since Aluminum remains in solid state within the considered temperature range, the Young's modulus E and the Poisson's ratio ν vs temperature are taken into account. The temperature dependence of these properties of Al phase, surveyed from literature data, are shown in Fig. 5 [42]. As far as the Sn phase is concerned, the couple of properties to characterize the elastic regime were bulk modulus K and shear modulus G , introduced in order to capture the elastic behaviour in both solid and liquid stages. The temperature-dependence of these properties, derived from literature data [43,44] is shown in Fig. 6. Since inelastic responses for PCM are expected during the thermal cycle, stress-strain curves for both Al and Sn constituents are required. Families of stress-strain curves for different temperature levels are presented shown in Fig. 7.

To capture rate-independent plasticity the following power law type isotropic hardening model is applied:

$$\sigma = \sigma_y + A\varepsilon_p^m \quad (11)$$

where ε_p is the plastic strain. The yield stress σ_y , the hardening modulus A and the hardening exponent m were identified from tensile curves of literature works on Al [45] and Sn [46], shown in Fig. 7a and b, respectively. The values of σ_{ys} , A and m parameters as functions of temperature are presented in Figs. 8 and 9 for Al and Sn, respectively.

3.4. Model geometry, boundary conditions and finite element model

The representative volume element (RVE) for the investigated Al-Sn system was developed on the bases of its heat-treated microstructure, when Sn appears in the form of spherical inclusions inside Al matrix. The so described model was already adopted in a preliminary work, being this microstructure observed in powder metallurgy [22,23] and heat-treated casting at moderate cooling rate products. The microstructure was confirmed those of several samples investigated in the present paper, as will be explained later.

The microstructure arrangement can reasonably be approximated by a spherical inclusion particle in a simple cubic unit cell model, whose geometrical parameters vary from tenths to some hundreds of μm according to the material processing conditions. In the present case the size of the radius R of the spherical inclusion was selected to 42 μm , corresponding to the size adopted for the preliminary work [27], which could be considered for the coarser particles observed in the presently investigated thermally cycled samples. The RVE for the material has been considered to be a cubic cell with the spherical Sn inclusion at its centre, as shown in Fig. 10a, where $\frac{1}{4}$ of the cubic cell (RVE) is represented. Phase volume consideration leads to a cubic cell side of (L_0) was 116 μm , in order to obtain 80:20 vol ratio between Al and Sn.

The boundary conditions for the mechanical analysis are presented in Fig. 10 b). A roller constraint is applied on the bottom face by setting normal displacement to zero along z -direction. For the two internal faces, the symmetry conditions are applied. For the remaining faces, symmetry conditions with free displacement as defined in COMSOL are selected. This option allows the plane to translate along the normal direction as a rigid body.

For the heat transfer analysis the temperature profile at the bottom of the RVE was set equal to the dilatometric experimental cycle, is given on the bottom face of the cell (See Fig. 10c), with uniform initial temperature set to 20 °C. As far as the thermal simulation is concerned, symmetry boundary conditions are defined on internal faces while defined the thermal insulation conditions are given on external and top faces.

As far as the finite element analyses are concerned, tetrahedral finite elements with quadratic serendipity shape functions were used. A finite element mesh with a maximum element size of approximately 6.4 μm was generated. The time-dependent study was selected with time step control applying the backward difference formula with an initial time step of 0.001s and a relative tolerance of 10^{-5} .

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Dilatometric tests performed on as-cast microstructure

The results of the first set of dilatometric tests can be represented by thermal response under the 1st, 2nd 3rd and 10th cycle of the as-cast sample subjected to the highest number of dilatometric cycles. Fig. 11 plots the thermal strains during each cycle ($\Delta L/L_0$) occurred in different cycles vs. temperature. Here, the thermal strain was zeroed at each thermal cycle, even if considering the same initial length of the sample (L_0), thus neglecting length changes induced by previous cycles.

The curves clearly show differences between the first and the later cycles, with the differences between heating and cooling paths being progressively reduced, leading to an improved form-stability of the material as the number of cycles increases. Fig. 11b shows the strain (the relative change of length, $\Delta L/L_0$) strain accumulated at the end of each cycle. The relative change of length at the end of dilatometric cycles, which displays compressive strain lower than 1 % at the first cycle, is drastically reduced at the end of the following two cycles, then becoming negligible and slightly increasing from the 3rd cycle on. Once removed from dilatometer, some exudated tin was observed, the amount of which was qualitatively not affected by the number of cycles following the first. This latter and the microstructural changes explained in the following contribute to explain the differences mainly noticed in the 1st dilatometric cycle.

The thermal cycles performed during dilatometric tests, which induced melting/solidification of the Sn phase, led to a modification of the alloy microstructure with respect to the initial, as cast, microstructure. Fig. 12 clearly shows that in the as-cast condition the microstructure is cellular/dendritic, characterized by columnar Al phase

Fig. 5. Young's modulus (a) and Poisson's ratio (b) vs temperature for Al after [42].

Fig. 6. Bulk modulus (a) and shear modulus (b) vs temperature for Sn after [43,44].

Fig. 7. Stress-strain curves for different temperature levels for a) Al after [45] and Sn after [46].

Fig. 8. Parameters in plasticity hardening model for Al. a) Yield stress, b) hardening modulus A, c) hardening.

surrounded by the segregated Sn phase, finally solidified at low temperature. This structure was at least partially cancelled after the 1st dilatometric cycle. The micrographs of the alloy structure after the 1st or the 2nd cycle show a microstructure with isolated globular or elongated Sn phase structures, with a tendency to form more globular but coarser structures as the number of cycles increased. The average equivalent diameter of the Sn globules was of 6.4 μm at the end of the first dilatometric cycle and increased up to 10.8 μm in the tenth cycle. The

globule size is in any case far from being homogeneous, the in equivalent diameter of Sn globules being of about 6 μm after the first cycle, of about 10 μm after the second, with some globules equivalent diameter greater than 20 μm .

The dilatometric curves can be explained on the basis of their microstructural investigations on metallographic sections of samples and of macroscopic observation on the samples.

These 2D images are compatible with the progressive destruction of

Fig. 9. Parameters in plasticity hardening model for Sn. a) Yield stress, b) hardening modulus A , c) hardening exponent m .

Fig. 10. a) The unit cell considered for C-PCM model (1/4 of it); b) thermal boundary conditions; c) mechanical boundary conditions.

Fig. 11. a) Dilatometric curves at different cycles of the as-cast sample cycled 10 times at 270 °C, with 5 min holding at the highest temperature. b) the relative change of length ($\Delta L/L_0$) at the end of each cycle.

the 3D cellular/dendritic structure toward the presence of isolated Sn globules in a microstructure spheroidization process. Correspondingly, the interconnection between Sn phase is progressively lost and the PCM Sn phase, surrounded by the high-melting Al phase. The mobility of Sn when in the molten state as well as its leaking out of the sample, is

prevented as isolated globules form [25]. The tendency to Sn leakage during dilatometric cycles was actually observed, with the formation of Sn droplets exudated from the surface, mainly during the first dilatometric cycle. The strong change of length taking place during the first dilatometric cycle has been attributed to the material leaked from the

Fig. 12. SEM micrographs of Al-Sn C-PCM in various conditions. a) As-cast condition, b) as-cast +1 cycle at 270 °C c) as-cast +10 cycle at 270 °C d) heat treatment at 250 °C for 3 h.

bottom surface of the sample above the melting temperature. The behaviour has been explained by the observation of some exudated Sn at the surface of the samples and of a flattened droplet of Sn formed on the bottom flat surface of the sample, resulting from the leakage of Sn, its tendency to form droplets due to the non-wettability on solid Al [30] and the small load applied at the sample/holder interface to ensure contact. The molten Sn exudated from the outer surface of the material. On the other hand, the exudation of Sn from the bottom surface during the first cycle could be responsible of the rapid increase in length above melting corresponded to the formation of Sn droplet/s. As the viscosity of the molten tin reduced during the time of holding close to the maximum temperature, the droplet/s flattened, rapidly decreasing the sample length. After the first cycle the exudation of Sn reduces and the droplet/s on bottom surface further flattened and possibly coalesced during the time span when Sn was in its molten state. This makes the differences between heating and cooling cycle less evident. Other specimens

displayed similar behaviour during the cycles performed on them.

In view of comparison with numerical model of the Al-Sn composite PCM behaviour, the dilatometric curve at the 3rd thermal cycle performed of as-cast sample has been selected (Fig. 13a). The curve in Fig. 13b gives the temperature dependence of the temperature-derivative of the previous curve vs. temperature (corresponding to the linear coefficient of thermal expansion of the material).

The experimental thermal strain exhibits a uniform slope both above and below the transition temperature of tin. In heating phase, the thermal strain increases when temperature increases, and, when the melting point is approached, a change of slope occurs around 230 °C. This is explained by the solid/liquid transition of the tin phase. In the transition region, the strain starts to stabilize, approaching a plateau-like regime. When the Sn transition temperature is reached, the thermocouple positioned next to the specimen measures a constant temperature, related to the phase change heat absorption. For this reason,

Fig. 13. Comparison between results of FEA model for dilatometric curves and representative experimental curves the form-stable condition for the first set of experimental data. a) relative length change (not %), b) coefficient of linear thermal expansion, calculated as temperature, after [25].

when melting occurs, the thermal strain shortly tends to a constant value. After the phase change, the strain increases with the temperature again. In the phase change range, a notable aspect is the difference observed between the transition temperature values associated with the processes of melting and solidification, as shown in Fig. 13b. In the various dilatometric tests the transition occurred between to the 224 °C of the 222 and 226 °C during heating and in the range 213–217 °C during cooling. This can be attributed to the thermal hysteresis, which delineates the temperature difference between the melting point and crystallization temperature.

The thermal cycles performed up to 250 and 270 °C on samples previously heat treated for 3 h at 250 °C have a different behaviour during the first cycle (Fig. 14), where compressive relative change of length ($\Delta L/L_0$), was observed. In this cycle, a relatively low slope of the dilatometric curves during the heating part of dilatometric tests with respect to further cycles.

After the first cycle the compressive ($\Delta L/L_0$) was lower than 1 % for the sample tested at the highest temperature, and of about 0.5 % for that heated at 250 °C. From the second cycle the relative change of length induced by a dilatometric cycle decreased below 0.1 % in both cases. The lower relative change of length at the lowest temperature and the further reduction of the relative change of length as the number of thermal cycles increased were observed for the heat-treated samples. The reduced slope of the curve during the heating part of the first heating cycle could be related to specimen setting on the equipment. From the second cycle on the features displayed by dilatometric curves were close to those displayed by initially as-cast samples. Thus, in both situations, from the 3rd cycle on the material can be considered as form-stable, independently on its initial microstructure.

4.2. Modelled thermal response

The relative change of length during the dilatometric cycle from 20 to 270 °C and back to the initial temperature, calculated as relative displacement between the upper and bottom flat and parallel surfaces of the RVE are presented in Fig. 13a, compared to an experimental result of the as-cast sample in a form-stable cycle. As far as the temperature adopted to plot numerical results, the average ones in RVE were considered at each time, which were previously checked to be almost homogeneous during Sn phase transition (when the maximum temperature inhomogeneity within RVE is expected).

The numerically calculated derivative of the relative change of length with respect to the temperature is given in Fig. 13b. In general, the numerical strain-temperature curve shows a satisfactory agreement with the experimental one. However, in the phase transition, regime

differences in thermal strains behaviour are observed. For the unit cell the numerically derived thermal strain increases after the solid-liquid phase transition, while the experimental thermal strain curve exhibits a plateau behaviour. The inertia of the furnace-controlling systems during the melting of Sn latent heat is released in heating (absorbed in cooling) can be considered to explain the presence of two opposite peaks in the temperature ranges where experimental Sn melting and solidification occur instead of the single temperature, independent of the heating/cooling for the numerical calculations.

Focusing on the end of the thermal cycle up to 270 °C, the numerical analysis predicts a relative shrinkage of 0.01 %, while the specimen experienced a higher compression strain of 0.04 %.

The numerical analyses results can also add information on local behaviour to the above overall thermal response of the RVE, since the stress and strain in it can be analysed in various points at different stages of heating and cooling.

Fig. 15 illustrates the distribution of the stress component in the vertical direction (σ_z) in all points of the RVE at different temperatures during the heating and cooling parts of the dilatometric cycle. The comparison of images clearly show that the stress distribution differs from the heating and cooling part of the thermal cycle and that in the Sn phase the stress is more homogeneous than in Al. In Sn a compressive state develops in during the whole heating phase, (accentuated after the Sn melting) and remains in compression till the onset of solidification, as σ_z in the low-melting phases becomes positive.

In Al the stress distribution is quite inhomogeneous. During heating a tensile σ_z develops at the regions laying far from the inclusion. The situation is inverted during cooling, particularly during as solidification and at these regions a minor compressive stress remains at the end of thermal cycle. Focusing the attention on the Al region close to Al/Sn interface, here at all temperatures the stress in vertical direction at the interface differs for points vertically aligned and points laying on the horizontal plane including the centre of Sn inclusion.

This is related to the fact that in the former points σ_z corresponds to circumferential stress since z-axis corresponds to the radial direction of the spherical inclusion; in the latter case σ_z corresponds to circumferential stress. Obviously, the same holds for ϵ_z . At the interface the maximum positive/negative stress σ_z (radial or circumferential with respect to the actual location) are reached in the cooling part of the curve, after Sn solidification.

The strain component in vertical direction (z-axis) at representative temperatures during the thermal cycle are displayed in Fig. 16. The homogeneous and positive strain of Sn phase with respect to its initial condition can be observed during the whole heating stage, with a sudden increase induced by Sn melting. After melting, to the beginning of

Fig. 14. Comparison between the relative change of length ($\Delta L/L_0$), in percentage, of dilatometric samples which tests have been performed in after heat treatment of the material at 250 °C for 3 h (a) and at 270 °C for 3 h (b).

Fig. 15. Distribution of normal stress σ_{zz} at different time steps. a) Heating, 227°C, b) heating, 233°C, c) heating, 270°C, d) cooling, 233°C, e) cooling, 227°C, f) cooling, 20.°

solidification during the cooling part of the thermal cycle, the strain in vertical direction inside Sn inclusion remains almost constant, as well as homogeneous. After solidification, strains in vertical direction drastically reduce in Sn, and reaches minimal negative values at the end of the cycle (Fig. 16e). During the whole thermal cycle, the strain in vertical direction in Al are quite inhomogeneous (even of opposite signs), particularly in the part of the heating cycle in which Sn phase is in the molten state. At the end of the thermal cycle the Al phase exhibits small, mainly compressive strains.

Four points were considered to explore the temperature-dependence of stress and strain: for Sn and Al those laying on opposite sides of the Sn/Al interface along the vertical symmetry axis of RVE ($\text{Sn}_{\text{interface}}$ and $\text{Al}_{\text{interface}}$, respectively), the Sn at the centre of the inclusion (Sn_{core}), and lastly the Al point laying on the upper flat face far from the Sn inclusion (Al_{edge}). Their positions are illustrated in Fig. 17a together with their associated names.

The strain developed in the z-direction (vertical) in the four reference points during the thermal cycle are presented in Fig. 17b, with data related to the heating part of the cycle drawn in solid lines, those of the cooling part of the cycle plotted in dashed lines. Fig. 17b clearly shows that during heating both points inside the Sn inclusion display a slightly higher strain than Al, with a sudden increase related to Sn melting, followed by a further strain increase as the temperature reaches its maximum. During heating, the strain in the point at the core of Sn phase is slightly higher than that experienced by the point close to the Sn interface. During cooling the trends are inverted and, at the end of the thermal cycle, a small positive strain with respect to the initial condition is experienced by the Sn at Sn_{core} and a small negative strain close to the surface ($\text{Sn}_{\text{interface}}$). The strains in Al phase in vertical direction at the furthest point from the inclusion (i.e. Al_{edge}) increase in a smoother way, with minor changes occurring in the temperature range within which Sn melting and solidification takes place. As a matter of fact, the Al matrix

Fig. 16. Distribution of normal strain ε_z at different time steps. a) Heating, 227°C, b) heating, 233°C, c) heating, 270°C, d) cooling, 233°C, e) cooling, 227°C, f) cooling, 20°C.

acts as a constraint to this expansion, leading to a more complex stress distribution (Fig. 15), where compressive stress in z direction develops during heating close to the Sn inclusion, while tensile stress in z direction arises far from these regions. At the end of the thermal cycle negligible strain in vertical direction is noticed at Al_{edge} .

The evolution of strain in vertical direction is more complex for the point at the Al/Sn interface ($Al_{interface}$). During heating, the local strain here progressively reduces with respect Al-phase those predictable by thermal expansion only. During the melting of Sn inclusion vertical strains at this point of Al phase drastically reduce. Strains are minimally changed by heating to 270 °C. During cooling range in which Sn is in the molten state, the thermal strain in vertical direction at $Al_{interface}$ reduces, then rapidly increases during the Sn phase solidification occurs and Sn inclusion shrinks. The final cooling reduces the leads to a compressive strain in vertical direction in the point of Al interface.

Fig. 17c illustrates the von Mises equivalent stresses (σ_{eq}) for several temperature values considered in FE analyses. The yield stress (σ_y) in Al

and Sn introduced in Section 3.3 are also presented. σ_y can be compared to σ_z suggested by the colour scale in Fig. 15. Focusing at first the attention of the Al phase, at Al_{edge} , tensile stress σ_z increases by taking a maximum value of about 8–10 MPa when Sn is molten and becomes negative after Sn re-solidification by reaching a maximum compressive value of about 25 MPa at RT. Even if after Sn solidification its σ_z overcomes σ_y , the almost zero σ_{eq} at various temperatures prevents plastic deformation of the Al phase at this point. On the other hand, in the region close to Al interface the equivalent stress overcomes the yield point of Al already before 227 °C, triggering local plastic deformation. From the onset of Sn melting temperature of 270 °C, σ_{eq} displays coherent evolution with the deviation from almost linear increase in vertical strains before Sn melting and to the sudden drop of strain at melting (Fig. 17b).

The strain in the Al region surrounding the Sn inclusion leads to compressive strain in the Al phase along the radial direction with respect to the spherical inclusion (corresponding to z-direction at $Al_{interface}$) and

Fig. 17. a) Location of the reference points in Al and Sn phase. b) Evolution of strain vertical direction (ϵ_z) at reference points the same thermal cycle. Solid lines represent the heating stage whereas the dashed ones the cooling step; c) Evolution of von Mises equivalent stress (σ_{eq}) at reference points during thermal cycle up to 270 °C.

extension in circumferential directions. The Sn solidification and the final cooling reduces the compressive σ_z , while σ_{eq} increases, remaining lower than σ_y at corresponding temperatures.

The stress evolution in the Sn inclusion does not significantly change through the phase and is analysed focusing on the interface. A compressive stress σ_z (radial stress for the inclusion) develops inside the inclusion as a result of a higher thermal expansion coefficient than that of Al. It increases up to the onset of plastic deformation. The von Mises equivalent stress σ_{eq} in Sn points never overcome the yield point during the whole parts of the cycle in which the phase is in solid state, even if σ_e approached σ_y of Sn close to its melting (0.2 MPa).

The FE analysis with elasto-plastic models for Al and Sn phases thus suggest that the plastic deformation of the only regions of Al phase surrounding the Sn inclusion accommodates its expansion during heating and melting. As a result, the Al region that remains mostly deformed in compression at the end of the cycle, with a plastic strain that is in any case less than 0.1 %. The role of the inclusion/surrounding region on the overall behaviour of the material is evident.

The overall compressive strain predicted by the modelled dilatometric cycle on RVE is coherent to experimental dilatometric tests, with predicted final strains lower than experimental ones, for which a relatively high degree of form-stability can be stated. The observed tendency to reduce the accumulated strain, leading to proper form stability is worth to be demonstrated by models. On the basis of the results presented in this paper, the authors are setting up a new study on this, also considering the presence of creep, for different inclusion sizes and porosities in view of the optimization of the thermomechanical response and form-stability of C-PCMs.

5. Conclusions

The aim of this study was to assess the form stability of the Al-Sn C-PCM alloy either by experimental (dilatometric) tests and numerical analysis during thermal cycles across the phase transition of the low-melting phase that correspond to the service conditions. The overall thermo-mechanical behaviour of a modelled RVE has been analysed and compared to experimental results. The local thermomechanical behaviour of Al and Sn phases was then studied focusing on selected reference points. The following conclusions are drawn.

- The investigated C-PCM alloys display a certain microstructural stability, at least with respect to the microstructure developed during the first thermal cycle allowing the phase transformation of the low-

melting Sn phase. The microstructural changes reduced the mobility of molten Sn and its tendency to leak from outer surfaces.

- The dilatometric cycles performed on as-produced and heat treated samples displayed a progressive tendency to form stability, which can be considered reached from the third cycle on.
- The slopes of the dilatometric curve during the heat-up and cool-down stages is well reproduced by the model.
- Basic features of stress and strain states during the whole thermal cycle are reproduced by the simple model. It clearly shows the plastic deformation in Al regions surrounding Sn particles and thus the role of the inclusion/surrounding region on the overall behaviour of the material.

Future studies should be related to systematic numerical analysis of the effect of different heat cycle parameters (maximum temperature, number of cycles etc.) on the thermo-mechanical response and form stability of the composite PCM.

Furthermore, the effect of microstructural features, such as the size of inclusion and RVE dimensions and relative content of Sn, should be investigated numerically. Studies on the microstructure development of Sn during the hold time and thermal cycling should be performed in order identify situations where there is the need to account for microstructure changes. A thermo-mechanical phase mixture model should be developed and utilized inside the finite element software.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Elisabetta Gariboldi: Writing – original draft, Validation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Matteo Molteni:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Diego Andree Vargas Vargas:** Software, Investigation, Data curation. **Konstantin Naumenko:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Elisabetta Gariboldi, Konstantin Naumenko reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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